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Distributed Data-Driven Control and Optimization

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Abstract

In the field of Control and Optimization, there is a growing interest on data-driven learning algorithms, as an alternative to modeling based on first principles, and on distributed and multi-agent systems, which arise in many applications such as power systems, traffic management, and robotics. This thesis focuses on multi-agent systems with Linear Time-Invariant dynamics. Conditions for data-driven distributed system identification using persistently exciting inputs are derived, and a scheme for distributed closed-loop stabilization is proposed. Additionally, a parallel solver for Linear Matrix Inequalities is introduced, so that also the computation of the stabilization gain is not centralized.

The climb is less steep when there is someone who stands by you.

To my Family

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Chapter 1

Motivation and Literature Review

The effectiveness of control design relies on the model of the controlled system, which requires adequate modeling techniques and to collect and process data appropriately; making a proper design can be a challenging problem because of the various conditions and applications, and researchers have been experimenting various directions.

Classical model-based and system identification techniques can potentially be inefficient and expensive to characterize a system (e.g., in human-in-the-loop applications, or fluid dynamics), especially considering systems with a high degree of complexity, increasingly present in several applications .

Willems and coauthors showed in [1] that persistently exciting data can represent the input/output behavior of a linear system, and thereafter a growing interest in literature pointed to techniques where properly set up data define a non-parametric model. This implies simplifying the identification of a system, and parameter identification procedures based on prediction error or maximum likelihood can be avoided.

Following this approach De Persis *et al.* derived a parametrization of linear feedback systems in [2] which allowed to solve control problems such as state and output feedback stabilization, and the linear quadratic regulation, using data-dependent Linear Matrix Inequalities (LMIs, in preliminaries, Chapter 2) only; relations between state-space and data-based representations have been derived.

In [3], a data-enabled predictive control (DeePC) algorithm shown to be equivalent to the well-known Model Predictive Control (MPC) algorithm in the case of deterministic Linear Time-Invariant systems has been proposed. It computes optimal and safe control policies using real-time feedback driving the unknown system along a desired trajectory while satisfying system constraints. The non-parametric system model is used to predict future trajectories.

On the other hand, control design is more and more dealing with applications as UAV swarms ([4],[5]), transportation networks ([6],[7]), large-scale chemical processes([8]), distributed generation systems and smart grids ([9]). These are some examples of current and future applications regarding the evolving area of control and optimization of multi-agent systems (MASs) where the collective action plays a key role.

The main ideas commonly behind centralized, decentralized and distributed system are shown in Figure 1.1.

Usually in decentralized systems each agent applies inputs related to its own condition and evaluated without communicating with other agents, whereas in distributed systems each agent interacts with the neighbors also for the computation of its policy, and this could be a relevant feature when dynamics are coupled. Before taking action, each agent could be required to find an agreement with the other agents on the policy to apply; this is generally referred to as consensus.

Figure 1.1: Conventional concepts of Centralized, Decentralized and Distributed Systems

1.1 Multi-Agent System Control in literature

Different approaches have been experimented in literature to address various control problems related to multi-agent systems; some examples are described hereafter.

In [6], [7] problems related to large-scale systems, where not directly controlled agents are not supposed to cooperate with the others, are modeled as congestion games.

Here, in order to achieve some objectives for the system as a whole, as minimum agent density or shifting the game towards a maximum social output, the optimization is focused on designing and imposing optimal tolls.

For task assignment problems, a distributed market-based coordination algorithm, where agents make bids based on an underlying control law, has been proposed by Michael *et al.* in [10].

Agents are assumed to have knowledge of all tasks and of the maximum number of agents that can be assigned to every individual task. Each auction is performed among neighboring groups of agents and requires only local communication. It's shown that a desired assignment of agents to tasks is always achieved after exploring at most a polynomial number of assignments, dramatically reducing the combinatorial nature of discrete assignment problems; however, no global cost is optimized.

Assignment problems are related also to resource allocation problems, and belong to the more general category of transportation or Optimal Transport Problems (OTP).

Examples of works concerning MASs following this approach are the formation control problems presented in [5] and [11].

In [5], each agent first estimates the current swarm distribution in a distributed manner using a consensus algorithm and then solves the OTP to determine transition probabilities, so to obtain its guidance trajectory while avoiding collisions. Each agent thus independently determines its own trajectory so that the swarm density distribution converges to the desired formation. Guidance trajectories can be implemented through MPC.

In [11] a scalable, distributed iterative algorithm for large-scale optimal transport of collectives of autonomous agents is presented, based on a PDE model. The problem is formulated as steering the collective towards a target probability measure while minimizing the total cost of transport.

At each stage of the transport, the agents first implement an online, distributed primal-dual algorithm to obtain local estimates of the Kantorovich potential for optimal transport, considering target distribution; then they implement the transport by a proximal point algorithm.

Figure 1.2: Coordination scheme of the DRTO approach in [8]

It takes advantage of predicting the interaction between the distributed MPCs and the full plant response in the DRTO formulation.

Generally, Model Predictive Control has been already applied to agents constituting distributed systems in a variety of applications and in different manners, seen the MPC ability to optimize a cost and to guarantee robustness and safety.

For instance, [12] describes an on-demand collision avoidance strategy via Distributed MPC, applied to multi-agent point-to-point transitions of a quadrotors swarm.

The agents check for future collisions using the latest predicted states of the neighbours, computed at the time step before; the optimization problem is set up, including state and actuation constraints, and collision constraints are implemented only if required; after obtaining the next optimal sequence, that will be shared with the neighbors, the first element is applied to the model and the agents move one step ahead. The process is repeated until all agents reach their desired goals.

In the context of industrial processes control with objectives based on plant economics or set-point target tracking, a dynamic real-time optimization (DRTO) formulation with closed-loop prediction has been presented by Li and Swartz in [8].

The DRTO system communicates with the underlying MPC subsystems through time-varying set-point trajectories that are calculated based on consecutive predictions of the closed-loop response of the plant under the distributed MPC system.

In [9], the distributed model predictive controller for the LFC of the multi-area power system is designed. The controllers in each area exchange their measurements and predictions (inputs, states) by communication and incorporate the information from other controllers into their own optimization so as to coordinate with each other.

Comparisons of response to step load change, computational burden and robustness have been made between DMPC (Distributed MPC), centralized MPC and decentralized MPC, where the introduced distributed MPC technique emerged.

Another problem of interest is the stabilization of multi-agent systems, via state-feedback control. Methods to obtain a gain with a *distributed structure* (the control input of an agent can depend only on states of agents (agent itself included) affecting the dynamics of the agent, this structure may be inferred by the global state matrix) are proposed in [13] and [14], where Linear Matrix Inequalities are solved to satisfy the related Lyapunov stability condition, ensuring that the computed gain matrix has the desired structure.

1.1.1 Consensus

As mentioned before, in some cases it could be required that a common agreement before taking action has to be reached.

The network has therefore to solve an optimal consensus problem, where the agents locally cooperate by exchanging some information (as their own state), in view of optimizing a global objective.

Agents might be subject to state and input constraints, as dynamics and coupling constraints. Consensus might have to be reached between more agents and also a leader, when there is one.

[4] is an example of a formation control problem with collision avoidance in a Multi-UAV system, where the leader generates the reference state trajectory. A consensus-based cooperative control algorithm is applied to fly cooperatively in formation, with UAVs following the leader, and a leader-follower structure is employed to achieve the individual objective of generating a geometric configuration of the formation. The leader individually provides the only directly connected UAVs with its own position and desired positions for formation. Each UAV considers the others reference state trajectories as constant information while optimizing its tracking.

In [15], DMPC is employed to optimize a coupled objective function while respecting state and input constraints. The designed consensus algorithm is based on the Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers (ADMM), which combines features of the method of multipliers (robustness) and of dual decomposition (decomposability).

It is shown to yield closed-loop performance near what is achieved through centralized optimization with few tens of iterations.

1.1.2 Network Modeling

In the case of multi-agent systems with a given network topology, graph theoretic methods are often employed in literature to model the dynamics, as also in [15], described above.

As illustrated in Chapter 2 (preliminaries), agents are modeled as vertices and interconnections as edges, thus the system is represented as a graph; the related information is used to derive the Laplacian matrix, involved in the dynamics.

Interestingly, the second smallest eigenvalue of the Laplacian, called algebraic connectivity, represents a lower bound for node connectivity, i.e. the minimum number of nodes that must be removed to disconnect a graph or render it a node only (trivial graph); in the context of a consensus algorithm, an higher algebraic connectivity means faster convergence.

In a network where n is the number of nodes (or vertices) and D is the *network diameter* (longest distance between two nodes), algebraic connectivity's lower bound, in turn, is $4/(nD)$: convergence rate increases with smaller diameters.

Laplacian eigenvalues have also relevant properties in *Cartesian networks* (where the vertex set is the Cartesian product of the *factor* graphs' vertex sets, as in [16]) and multi-layered systems ([17], [18], where there are network-of-networks systems with multiple time-scales).

1.2 About this thesis

The aim of this work is to introduce schemes for distributed identification and for distributed stabilization of Linear Time Invariant (LTI) multi-agent systems, following the previously mentioned results on data-driven representation and the matrix inequality based design method for consensus derived by Zhai *et al.* in [13]. Differently from [13] and [14], the discrete-time stabilization is considered and no assumption is made on the graph describing the system. As a result, another contribution of this thesis is a parallel framework to solve the matrix inequalities.

The remainder of this work is structured as follows. In Chapter 2, some preliminaries about concepts employed in this thesis are given. The scheme and the conditions for the proposed Distributed System Identification are derived in Chapter 3. Chapter 4 describes a novel method to compute a gain matrix enabling distributed stabilization, and introduces a parallel solver for the computations. Implementation of the schemes explained in Chapter 3 and 4, and related experiments on example systems, are shown in Chapter 5. Finally, the results of this thesis are summarized and future directions are outlined in Chapter 6.

I would like to thank Dr. Mathias Hudoba De Badyn for the constant interest he has shown in the topics I proposed for this thesis, by giving me useful suggestions to develop them.

Chapter 2

Preliminaries

2.1 Graph-Theoretic methods for Multi-Agent Systems

Relations between agents of a multi-agent system can be represented by a graph $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ with the set of N nodes $\mathcal{V} = [0, 1, \dots, N]$ and edges $\mathcal{E} \subset \mathcal{V} \times \mathcal{V}$.

Each node corresponds to an agent that has inputs and outputs of interest, and which may be able to make computations and decisions; edges correspond to interconnections, as dependencies or communication links, and can be directed, meaning that the interconnection is not mutual.

For an agent i , the neighbor agents set is defined as

$$\mathcal{N}_i := \{j \in \mathcal{V} \mid (i, j) \in \mathcal{E}\} \quad \text{or} \quad \mathcal{N}_i := \{j \in \mathcal{V} \mid (j, i) \in \mathcal{E}\}, \quad (2.1)$$

where, for a directed graph, the definition at the left indicates the *outgoing* neighbors, while the one at the right the *incoming* neighbors; for an undirected graph, the definitions are equivalent.

The adjacency matrix of a graph $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ is a square $|\mathcal{V}| \times |\mathcal{V}|$ matrix \mathcal{A} such that its element $\mathcal{A}(i, j)$ is one when there is an edge from vertex i to vertex j , or between i and j in case of undirected graph, and zero when there is no edge. An example is shown below.

The degree matrix of an undirected graph with N nodes is a $N \times N$ diagonal matrix where the (i, i) element is the degree of node i , i.e. the number of edges connected to i .

In a directed graph, in-degree (the number of incoming edges at each vertex) or out-degree (the number of outgoing edges at each vertex) may be the properties to which the term degree refers to.

The Laplacian matrix L of a simple graph (unweighted, undirected graph containing no self-loops or multiple edges, which connect two same nodes), is defined as the difference between the degree matrix D and the adjacency matrix \mathcal{A} :

$$L = D - \mathcal{A}.$$

By considering the edges of the graph in the figure above as undirected, the graph Laplacian L would be:

$$L = \begin{bmatrix} 2 & -1 & -1 \\ -1 & 2 & -1 \\ -1 & -1 & 2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2.2)$$

2.2 Data-based system representation and *Willems et al.'s Fundamental Lemma*

The Fundamental Lemma introduced by Willems *et al.* ([1]), and revisited by De Persis *et al.* ([2]) to obtain results employed in this work, provides conditions for which it's possible to describe any finite trajectory of a Linear Time Invariant (LTI) system as a linear combination of a finite number of trajectories, generated from the same system and having the same time span.

More specifically, given that $\mathcal{H}_\tau(w^d)$ refers to the Hankel matrix of the signal w^d , which has $\tau \leq T$ block rows and $(T - \tau + 1)$ columns, i.e.

$$\mathcal{H}_\tau(w^d) = \begin{bmatrix} w^d(0) & w^d(1) & \cdots & w^d(T - \tau) \\ w^d(1) & w^d(2) & \cdots & w^d(T - \tau + 1) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ w^d(\tau - 1) & w^d(\tau) & \cdots & w^d(T - 1) \end{bmatrix};$$

and that u^d is *persistently exciting of order $n + \tau$* if $\text{rowrank } \mathcal{H}_{n+\tau}(u^d) = m \cdot (n + \tau)$ (full row rank), being $u^d(k) \in \mathbb{R}^m \forall k \in [0, T - 1]$, a variant of the Lemma ([19]) stated in state-space form (the result was originally presented in the language of behavioral systems theory) can be enunciated.

Lemma 1. *Consider the LTI system $x(t + 1) = Ax(t) + Bu(t)$, with (A, B) controllable.*

Let $u^d : [0, T - 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$, $x^d : [0, T - 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ be sequences such that $w^d = (u^d, x^d)$ is a trajectory of the system and u^d is persistently exciting of order $n + \tau$. Then for any pair $u : [0, \tau - 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$, $x : [0, \tau - 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$, $w = (u, x)$ is a trajectory of the system if and only if there exists $g \in \mathbb{R}^{T+\tau-1}$ such that $\mathcal{H}_\tau(w^d)g = w$.

2.3 Frobenius Norm

In Chapter (3), the Frobenius norm is used in a system identification setting.

The Frobenius norm of a matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, denoted by $\|A\|_F$, is defined as (from [20]):

$$\|A\|_F = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n a_{ij}^2}, \quad (2.3)$$

where a_{ij} is the element of A at the row i and column j .

2.4 Linear Matrix Inequalities

Let the matrix $F \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$.

F is said to be *positive definite*, or

$$F > 0 \iff u^T F u > 0 \quad \forall u \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus \{0\}.$$

It can be noted that the notation

$$F > F_1, \tag{2.4}$$

means

$$u^T F u > u^T F_1 u \quad \forall u \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus \{0\} \tag{2.5}$$

which is equivalent to

$$u^T (F - F_1) u > 0 \quad \forall u \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus \{0\}, \text{ or } F - F_1 > 0. \tag{2.6}$$

Therefore,

$$F > F_1 \iff F - F_1 > 0. \tag{2.7}$$

Also, from (2.5) it's clear that if $F_1 > 0$, then $F > 0$.

A linear matrix inequality (LMI), as reported in [21], has the form

$$F(x) := F_0 + \sum_{i=1}^m x_i F_i > 0, \tag{2.8}$$

where $x \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the variable and the symmetric matrices $F_i = F_i^T \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $i = 0, \dots, m$, are given.

Nonstrict LMIs have the form

$$F(x) \geq 0 \quad (F(x) \text{ is positive semidefinite, i.e. } u^T F(x) u \geq 0 \quad \forall u \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus \{0\}).$$

Similar considerations can be made for inequalities of the form $F(x) < 0$, $F(x) \leq 0$, $F \leq F_1$, involving matrices that are not positive but negative definite or semidefinite :

$$F < 0 \implies u^T F u < 0 \quad \forall u \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus \{0\} \quad (\text{negative definite}), \tag{2.9}$$

$$F \leq 0 \implies u^T F u \leq 0 \quad \forall u \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus \{0\} \quad (\text{negative semidefinite}). \tag{2.10}$$

2.4.1 Schur Complement condition

Given the symmetric block matrix

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} Q & S \\ S^T & R \end{bmatrix},$$

where Q and R are square matrices, the *Schur complement* of Q in M and of R in M are respectively

$$M/Q = R - S^T Q^{-1} S, \quad (2.11)$$

$$M/R = Q - S R^{-1} S^T. \quad (2.12)$$

The following conditions hold:

$$\begin{aligned} M > 0 &\iff Q > 0, M/Q > 0, \\ M > 0 &\iff R > 0, M/R > 0, \\ \text{if } Q > 0 \text{ then } M \geq 0 &\iff M/Q \geq 0, \\ \text{if } R > 0 \text{ then } M \geq 0 &\iff M/R \geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

2.5 Linear quadratic Lyapunov theory - Stability of discrete time linear systems

Let $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $P = P^T \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $Q = Q^T \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$.

From the dynamics equation $x(t+1) = Ax(t)$ and $V(z) = z^T P z$, that is a Lyapunov function used to verify stability, it follows that $\Delta V(z) = -z^T Q z$, where P, Q satisfy the (discrete-time) Lyapunov equation $A^T P A - P + Q = 0$.

The system described by $x(t+1) = Ax(t)$ is (globally asymptotically) stable if

$$P > 0, Q > 0,$$

or, equivalently, if

$$A^T P A - P < 0.$$

Chapter 3

Distributed System Identification

The results obtained in this chapter enable the distributed learning of a multi-agent LTI system with properly collected data, where each agent identifies its dynamics.

It is also shown that in a homogeneous system, consisting of agents with similar state and input matrices, an agent with so-called complete dynamics can identify the global system if the network structure is given.

Examples on how to apply these findings are provided in Chapter 5.

Before all, in a multi-agent system an agent dynamics can depend not only on its own input and on its own state, but also on states and inputs of coupled or neighboring agents, as described below for an agent i of a MAS with LTI dynamics (so are the dynamics of every agent) whose set of neighbors is \mathcal{N}_i :

$$\mathbf{x}_i(t+1) = A_{ii}\mathbf{x}_i(t) + B_{ii}\mathbf{u}_i(t) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} A_{ij}\mathbf{x}_j(t) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} B_{ij}\mathbf{u}_j(t), \quad (3.1)$$

where \mathbf{x}_i and \mathbf{x}_j are state vectors, \mathbf{u}_i and \mathbf{u}_j input vectors, A_{ii} and A_{ij} are submatrices of the global system matrix A , and B_{ii} and B_{ij} submatrices of B , the global input matrix.

Generally, considered the set \mathcal{N} of all the agents and considering all the possible interdependencies, the relation can be expressed as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \vdots \\ \mathbf{x}_i(t+1) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{x}_j(t+1) \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \cdots & A_{ii} & \cdots & A_{ij} & \cdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \cdots & A_{ji} & \cdots & A_{jj} & \cdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \vdots \\ \mathbf{x}_i(t) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{x}_j(t) \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \cdots & B_{ii} & \cdots & B_{ij} & \cdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \cdots & B_{ji} & \cdots & B_{jj} & \cdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \vdots \\ \mathbf{u}_i(t) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{u}_j(t) \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3.2)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_i(t+1) = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} (A_{ij}\mathbf{x}_j(t) + B_{ij}\mathbf{u}_j(t)), \quad (3.3)$$

where A_{ij} B_{ij} and are null matrices if $j \notin \mathcal{N}_i$ and B_{ij} is a null matrix with $j \in \mathcal{N}_i$ when agent i equation doesn't depend on the j neighboring or coupled agent input.

Obviously, it is possible to express the dynamics of the whole system consisting of all the agents, referred to as *global*, in the form:

$$\mathbf{x}(t+1) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}(t), \quad (3.4)$$

with \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{u} containing respectively all the (agents) states and inputs.

As mentioned by De Persis *et al.* in [2] using the results from [20], a LTI system can be identified via the following minimization:

$$\min_{[B \ A]} \left\| X_{1,T} - [B \ A] \begin{bmatrix} U_{0,T} \\ X_{0,T} \end{bmatrix} \right\|_F \quad (3.5)$$

with

$$X_{t,T} = [x_d(t) \quad x_d(t+1) \quad \dots \quad x_d(t+T-1)]$$

$$U_{t,T} = [u_d(t) \quad u_d(t+1) \quad \dots \quad u_d(t+T-1)]$$

$$T \geq (m+1)n + m,$$

where $\|\cdot\|_F$ is the Frobenius norm, $x_d(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $u_d(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ are state samples and input samples of the global system at time step t respectively; it follows that $X_{t,T}$ and $U_{t,T}$, have the same number of rows of the samples they contain.

In (3.5), $U_{0,T}$ must be *persistently exciting* of order $n+1$.

Indeed, n and m represent the number of all agents' states and inputs.

Theorem 1. *Given the identification in (3.5), each row of $[B \ A]$ can be identified independently from the others.*

Proof. Referring to the difference in (3.5) :

$$DIF = X_{1,T} - [B \ A] \begin{bmatrix} U_{0,T} \\ X_{0,T} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3.6)$$

with each (i, t) entry given by

$$DIF(i, t) = X_{1,T}(i, t) - \sum_{j=1}^n (A(i, j)X_{0,T}(j, t)) - \sum_{k=1}^m (B(i, k)U_{0,T}(k, t)), \quad (3.7)$$

where n is the number of states, m of inputs, and $X_{r,T}(i, t)$ (i row and t column) is the state i sampled at step $t+r$, i.e. using the notation of above $x_d(t+r)$; a similar relation holds for $U_{0,T}(k, t)$.

Since the goal is to minimize the Frobenius norm of DIF , the identification consists in finding $[B \ A]$ which minimizes the square of the sum of all the elements of DIF_F , where

$$DIF_F(i, t) = DIF(i, t)^2 = \left(X_{1,T}(i, t) - \sum_{j=1}^n (A(i, j)X_{0,T}(j, t)) - \sum_{k=1}^m (B(i, k)U_{0,T}(k, t)) \right)^2. \quad (3.8)$$

Seen that DIF_F entries are nonnegative real numbers, the minimizer of the Frobenius norm is also the minimizer of just the sum of DIF_F elements

$$\operatorname{argmin}_{[B \ A]} \sum_i \sum_t DIF_F(i, t) = \operatorname{argmin}_{[B \ A]} \left\| X_{1,T} - [B \ A] \begin{bmatrix} U_{0,T} \\ X_{0,T} \end{bmatrix} \right\|_F; \quad (3.9)$$

then, solving (3.5) is equivalent to solve

$$\min_{[B \ A]} \sum_i \sum_t DIF_F(i, t) = \min_{[B \ A]} \sum_i C_F(i), \quad (3.10)$$

with $DIF_F = DIF_F([B \ A])$ and C_F the column sum:

$$C_F = \sum_t DIF_F(:, t).$$

From (3.8) it can be noted that the i -th row of $DIF_F^{(i)} = DIF_F(i, :)$ is a function of the i -th row of $[B(i, :) \ A(i, :)]$, i.e.

$$DIF_F^{(i)} = DIF_F^{(i)}([B(i, :) \ A(i, :)]);$$

so DIF_F can be rewritten as

$$DIF_F = \begin{bmatrix} \vdots \\ DIF_F^{(i)}([B(i, :) \ A(i, :)]) \\ DIF_F^{(i+1)}([B(i+1, :) \ A(i+1, :)]) \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3.11)$$

Naturally the same holds for the column sum C_F of DIF_F :

$$C_F = \begin{bmatrix} \vdots \\ C_F^{(i)}([B(i, :) \ A(i, :)]) \\ C_F^{(i+1)}([B(i+1, :) \ A(i+1, :)]) \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3.12)$$

with $C_F^{(i)} = C_F(i)$; each i row element of C_F ($C_F^{(i)}$) depends only on the i row of $[B \ A]$, hence, if $[B^{(i)} \ A^{(i)}] = [B(i, :) \ A(i, :)]$,

$$\min_{[B \ A]} \sum_i C_F^{(i)} = \sum_i \min_{[B^{(i)} \ A^{(i)}]} C_F^{(i)}, \quad (3.13)$$

that corresponds to (3.10), and so to solve (3.5).

Therefore

$$[B^{(i)} \ A^{(i)}] = \operatorname{argmin}_{[B^{(i)} \ A^{(i)}]} C_F^{(i)} = \operatorname{argmin}_{[B^{(i)} \ A^{(i)}]} \sum_t DIF_F(i, t), \quad (3.14)$$

that is, each row i of $[B \ A]$ can be identified separately from the others and its identification depends only on the i row of DIF_F ; clearly, there is a bijection between $[B^{(i)} \ A^{(i)}]$ and $C_F^{(i)}$. Furthermore, as can be noticed in (3.8), the square root of $\sum_t DIF_F(i, t)$ yields the following Frobenius norm:

$$\left\| X_{1,T}^{(i)} - [B^{(i)} \ A^{(i)}] \begin{bmatrix} U_{0,T} \\ X_{0,T} \end{bmatrix} \right\|_F, \quad (3.15)$$

which, for reasons mentioned above (3.8, 3.9), has the same minimizer $[B^{(i)} \ A^{(i)}]$ of $\sum_t DIF_F(i, t)$ (in (3.13)); hence

$$[B^{(i)} \ A^{(i)}] = \operatorname{argmin}_{[B^{(i)} \ A^{(i)}]} \left\| X_{1,T}^{(i)} - [B^{(i)} \ A^{(i)}] \begin{bmatrix} U_{0,T} \\ X_{0,T} \end{bmatrix} \right\|_F, \quad (3.16)$$

where $X_{1,T}^{(i)}$ is the i -th row of $X_{1,T}$.

□

Corollary 1.1. *Given the full system representation in (3.4), each agent can identify its dynamics independently.*

Proof. Each agent state dynamics is described by a subset of rows of (3.4), each of which independently identifiable according to Theorem 1. Moreover, different $[B \ A]$ rows can indeed be identified in a same minimization problem (3.13).

□

An interesting observation can also be made on the data required to identify each state dynamics, or each row of $[B \ A]$, which leads to the following corollary.

Corollary 1.2. *Data related to a state or an input known to not affect the i state are not needed to identify of the i -th row of $[B \ A]$.*

Proof. According to theorem 1, the identification of $[B^{(i)} \ A^{(i)}]$ depends on the i -th row of DIF_F , where each element is given by (3.8) :

$$DIF_F(i, t) = \left(X_{1,T}(i, t) - \sum_{j=1}^n (A(i, j) X_{0,T}(j, t)) - \sum_{k=1}^m (B(i, k) U_{0,T}(k, t)) \right)^2.$$

It can be observed that if an entry $A(i, j)$ or $B(i, k)$ is known to be zero, i.e. state i doesn't depend on state j or input k , related elements in the row $X_{0,T}(j, :)$ or $U_{0,T}(k, :)$ are multiplied by zero when computing the i row of DIF_F ($X_{0,T}(j, t)$ or $U_{0,T}(k, t)$ multiplied by zero for every t).

Thus if state i doesn't depend on state j or input k , the related row $X_{0,T}(j, :)$ or $U_{0,T}(k, :)$ is not needed to identify the i -th row of row of $[B \ A]$, and so the dynamics of state i .

This also means that (3.16) can be rewritten as

$$[\tilde{B}^{(i)} \ \tilde{A}^{(i)}] = \operatorname{argmin}_{[\tilde{B}^{(i)} \ \tilde{A}^{(i)}]} \left\| X_{1,T}^{(i)} - [\tilde{B}^{(i)} \ \tilde{A}^{(i)}] \begin{bmatrix} U_{0,T}^{(Di)} \\ X_{0,T}^{(Di)} \end{bmatrix} \right\|_F, \quad (3.17)$$

where $\tilde{B}^{(i)}$ contains only the non zero elements of $B^{(i)}$, $\tilde{A}^{(i)}$ the non zero elements of $A^{(i)}$, while $U_{0,T}^{(Di)}$ and $X_{0,T}^{(Di)}$ refer to the collected data of inputs and states, respectively, which affect state i dynamics.

□

Corollary 1.3. *The dynamics of an agent i with the following form (same notation of (3.1))*

$$\mathbf{x}_i(t+1) = A_{ii}\mathbf{x}_i(t) + B_{ii}\mathbf{u}_i(t) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} A_{ij}\mathbf{x}_j(t), \quad (3.18)$$

needs only collected data of its own state, input, and of coupled agents' states to be identified.

Proof. The dynamics (3.18) indicate that the evolution of each variable of the state of agent i x_i can depend only on agent i own state, input and on coupled agent states x_j . Therefore, as shown in Corollary 1.2, collected data not related to these states and inputs are not needed to identify the dynamics of any entry of the state of agent i . □

Remark 1. According to Corollary 1.2 and 1.3, the dynamics of an agent requires only data related to the agent itself and to neighbors or coupled agents to be identified.

Therefore, in a setting where each agent collects data referring to its state and input, only a local exchange of data is needed to allow each agent to identify its own dynamics equation, enabling a distributed identification of the global system.

Remark 2. The dynamics equation of a state, i.e. a row of $[B \ A]$, or of an agent, can also be identified independently via (3.5) by considering the state or the agent as a separate system; however, this would imply considering coupled states as part of the input (as in [19]), which has to be persistently exciting of related order. Generating a persistently exciting signal made also of states is more difficult, since states follow the global dynamics equation.

So far, it has been shown that each agent can identify its own dynamics equation independently and by using only collected data affecting it.

By having now a look on the global system, what can be said if agents have similar dynamics?

3.1 Global System Identification from Local Dynamics

This section focuses on multi-agent systems consisting of agents which have similarities in their dynamics that can allow each agent to identify the global dynamics equation independently.

As can be seen in (3.1)

$$\mathbf{x}_i(t+1) = A_{ii}\mathbf{x}_i(t) + B_{ii}\mathbf{u}_i(t) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} A_{ij}\mathbf{x}_j(t) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} B_{ij}\mathbf{u}_j(t), \quad (3.19)$$

each agent i dynamics can be not only described by a state matrix at A_{ii} and an input matrix at B_{ii} , but also by coupling state matrices at A_{ij} and input matrices at B_{ij} which are non-null when an agent i depends respectively on states or inputs of another agent j .

From now on, a multi-agent system where state and input matrices at A_{ii} and at B_{ii} are the same for every agent i as well as the non-null coupling matrices at A_{ij} and at B_{ij} for the agents having related couplings, will be referred to as homogeneous MAS.

If these common matrices A_{ii} , B_{ii} , A_{ij} , B_{ij} are labeled respectively as A_o , B_o , A_c , B_c , for an homogeneous MAS 3.1 can be rewritten as:

$$\mathbf{x}_i(t+1) = A_o\mathbf{x}_i(t) + B_o\mathbf{u}_i(t) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} A_c\mathbf{x}_j(t) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} B_c\mathbf{u}_j(t). \quad (3.20)$$

Hereinafter, an agent is said to have a *complete dynamics* with respect to the MAS if its dynamics contain all the (common) matrices describing the dynamics of the other agents.

Theorem 2. *In a homogeneous MAS described by (3.20), a complete dynamics and the adjacency matrices describing states and inputs interdependencies are sufficient to identify the global system.*

Proof. The system matrix A of a generic homogeneous MAS looks like:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} A_o & 0 & A_c & 0 & \dots \\ A_c & A_o & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & A_o \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3.21)$$

where, as mentioned previously, A_o is the common state matrix at A_{ii} for any agent i of the system and A_c the common non-null coupling matrix at A_{ij} when the states of agent i depend on the states of another agent j .

Clearly, the main-diagonal blocks of A are A_o matrices; also, when the state of agent i is coupled to the state of another agent j , at A_{ij} there is A_c instead of a null block matrix .

Indeed, the system matrix of the generic global system at issue can be seen as the sum of two block matrices Ad and Aa as shown below (referring to (3.21)) :

$$A = Ad + Aa = \begin{bmatrix} A_o & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots \\ 0 & A_o & 0 & 0 & \cdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & A_o \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & A_c & 0 & \cdots \\ A_c & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3.22)$$

where Ad is a block diagonal matrix whose non-null block matrices are all equal to A_o , or

$$Ad = I_N \otimes A_o \quad (\text{Kronecker product, system of } N \text{ agents}), \quad (3.23)$$

and Aa blocks Aa_{ij} are either null or A_c if the state of agent i depends the state of another agent j ; this block structure of Aa can be described by the adjacency matrix \mathcal{A}_A of a directed graph showing the interdependencies between agents states, allowing to express Aa as

$$Aa = \mathcal{A}_A \otimes A_c, \quad (3.24)$$

$$Aa = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & A_c & 0 & \cdots \\ A_c & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathcal{A}_A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \cdots \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3.25)$$

As a matter of fact, it's possible to consider a directed graph where the nodes are representing agents states, and the directed edges indicate whether a state depends or another state or not. If an edge directed from node i to j indicates that states of agent i depend on states of j , the (i, j) entry of a related adjacency matrix \mathcal{A}_A is 1, and as seen before the block Aa_{ij} has to be a A_c .

On the other hand, an edge directed in the opposite direction only, i.e. from node j to i , means that the states of agent i don't depend on the states of agent j , even if the states of agent j depend on the states of agent i , so in this case the (i, j) entry of \mathcal{A}_A is zero and the block Aa_{ij} has to be a null matrix; no edge between i and j indicates that there are no dependencies between the states of agent i and j , thus also in this case $\mathcal{A}_A(i, j) = 0$ and the block matrix Aa_{ij} is null.

Consequently, A_c and \mathcal{A}_A are sufficient to identify Aa , while A_o and the number of agents -given by the size of \mathcal{A}_A - are sufficient to identify Ad : A_c , A_o , and the adjacency matrix \mathcal{A}_A are sufficient to identify A .

A similar result can be obtained for B following the same procedure:

$$B = Bd + Ba, \quad (3.26)$$

$$Bd = I_N \otimes B_o, \quad (3.27)$$

$$Ba = \mathcal{A}_B \otimes B_c. \quad (3.28)$$

If \mathcal{A}_B is the adjacency matrix of a graph similar to the one of \mathcal{A}_A (describing how the inputs of each agent affect the other agents states), B_o is the block matrix expressing the dependence of an agent on its own inputs (as A_o does for the own states), while B_c on another agent inputs (A_c), then B_c , B_o , and \mathcal{A}_B are sufficient to identify B .

By definition, A_c or B_c is contained in the so-called complete dynamics whenever there is an agent in the MAS depending on another agent's state or input respectively. So A_c or B_c is present in the complete dynamics when it is a submatrix describing the global system state or input matrix together with A_o or B_o and the null submatrix; this means that complete dynamics contain all the matrices needed to identify the global system together with the adjacency matrices \mathcal{A}_A and \mathcal{A}_B , which indicate where A_c or B_c have to be placed whenever the related interdependencies exist. \square

Corollary 2.1. *In a homogeneous MAS, the adjacency matrices \mathcal{A}_A , \mathcal{A}_B allow to verify that an agent dynamics is complete.*

Proof. As observable from (3.22), (3.24) and (3.25), the coupling matrix A_c exists and it is needed to determine the global state matrix A only when \mathcal{A}_A is a non null matrix.

A similar reasoning can be applied to \mathcal{A}_B . Therefore with a comparison between the matrices in an agent dynamics equation and the required ones according to the adjacency matrices it's possible to verify that the dynamics equation at issue is complete. \square

Corollary 2.2. *In a homogeneous MAS, if there are coupled states, the global state matrix A is given by*

$$A = I_N \otimes A_o + \mathcal{A}_A \otimes A_c , \quad (3.29)$$

otherwise

$$A = I_N \otimes A_o . \quad (3.30)$$

Similarly, if there are states depending on other agents' inputs, the global input matrix B can be computed as

$$B = I_N \otimes B_o + \mathcal{A}_B \otimes B_c , \quad (3.31)$$

otherwise

$$B = I_N \otimes B_o , \quad (3.32)$$

Proof. It is a direct result of what shown in Theorem 2, and in particular of (3.22), (3.23), (3.24) for A , and (3.26), (3.27), (3.28) for B . \square

Remark 3. According to Corollary 2.1 and 2.2, given the mentioned adjacency matrices and after identifying its dynamics equation, each agent of a homogeneous MAS can check that its dynamics is complete and, if so, it can identify the global system equation starting from the local equation.

Corollary 2.3. *In the homogeneous MAS described by (3.18), where every agent has its state coupled, each agent can identify the global system equation from the local one, given the adjacency matrix \mathcal{A}_A .*

Proof. Since every agent dynamics contains the same submatrices A_o , A_c and B_o , in this case every agent has complete dynamics. Following the results obtained above, with the adjacency matrix for the states \mathcal{A}_A each agent can identify the global dynamics equation from the local one. \square

Corollary 2.4. *In a homogeneous MAS where every agent has the same dynamics, each agent can identify the global system equation from the local one, given the needed adjacency matrices.*

Proof. Every agent is described by the same dynamics equation, hence every agent has a complete dynamics equation. \square

Chapter 4

Distributed Stabilization

The main focus of automatic control is to drive system states or outputs towards a desired trajectory; a central problem is the state feedback stabilization of a system around a target with related closed-loop guarantees, as in [2] and [13].

Distributed and multi-agent systems in general have the advantage to be modular, countering the need of a high-performance central processor and ensuring an higher degree of fault-tolerance. Generally in these systems the agents have access to local (so, partial) information only, while the global system response, to be driven to the desired target, depends on their collective actions (inputs).

This chapter therefore focuses not only on the computation of a stabilizing gain with a structure, in this case distributed (see Section 1.1, but also on setting a computation to be performed in a non-centralized manner, where each agent computes contributes to solve a part of the whole problem in parallel with the others.

First of all, considering the system in (3.1),

$$\mathbf{x}_i(t+1) = A_{ii}\mathbf{x}_i(t) + B_{ii}\mathbf{u}_i(t) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} A_{ij}\mathbf{x}_j(t) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} B_{ij}\mathbf{u}_j(t), \quad (4.1)$$

the proposed collective input for a distributed closed-loop stabilization of the global system is of the form

$$\begin{bmatrix} \vdots \\ \mathbf{u}_i(t) \\ \mathbf{u}_{i+1}(t) \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \vdots \\ K_i \\ K_{i+1} \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_1(t) \\ \mathbf{x}_2(t) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{x}_j(t) \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ K_{i,1} & K_{i,2} & \cdots & K_{ij} & \cdots \\ K_{i+1,1} & K_{i+1,2} & \cdots & K_{i+1,j} & \cdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_1(t) \\ \mathbf{x}_2(t) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{x}_j(t) \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4.2)$$

where

$$\mathbf{u}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \vdots \\ \mathbf{u}_i(t) \\ \mathbf{u}_{i+1}(t) \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix}, \quad K = \begin{bmatrix} \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ K_{i,1} & K_{i,2} & \cdots & K_{ij} & \cdots \\ K_{i+1,1} & K_{i+1,2} & \cdots & K_{i+1,j} & \cdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{x}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_1(t) \\ \mathbf{x}_2(t) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{x}_j(t) \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4.3)$$

with K referred to as gain or gain matrix; the block matrix at K_{ij} for any agents i and j is null if the state of agent i doesn't depend on j states or inputs, i.e.

$$j \notin \mathcal{N}_i \implies K_{ij} = 0 . \quad (4.4)$$

Given the distributed structure of the gain matrix, each agent i input vector \mathbf{u}_i depends only on states of agents affecting agent i dynamics, and the aim of this chapter is to introduce a method to compute a gain matrix K which stabilizes the global or collective system, where each K_i block in (4.2) for any agent i can be computed separately from the other blocks.

In this way, the whole stabilization process is non-centralized: the gain is obtained with a computation made in parallel, and each agent needs only local information to apply a proper input, thus following a distributed control scheme.

4.1 Gain computation

4.1.1 Discrete time Closed-Loop stability

Considering the global system with discrete-time dynamics introduced in (3.4)

$$\mathbf{x}(t+1) = A\mathbf{x}(t) + B\mathbf{u}(t) , \quad (4.5)$$

a gain K stabilizes the closed-loop system if the following Lyapunov condition is satisfied:

$$(A + BK)P(A + BK)^T - P < 0 , \quad (4.6)$$

where P is a symmetric positive-definite matrix.

The matrix inequality (4.6) is nonlinear and, as pointed out in [22], the multi-agent discrete time Lyapunov condition has not been well studied.

In the following sections, methods to solve (4.6) with LMI software and in parallel by the computing agents, are presented.

4.1.2 The homotopy method for the continuous time case

Zhai *et al.* proposed in [13, 23] a homotopy based method to solve the bilinear matrix inequality related to the continuous time case with a structured gain, which is:

$$(A + BK)^T P + P(A + BK) < 0 \quad , \quad (4.7)$$

where P is a symmetric positive-definite matrix.

The described method consists in solving iteratively the following inequality for the matrix function F

$$F_1(P) + \mu F_2(P, K) = F(P, K, \mu) < 0 \quad , \quad (4.8)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} F_1(P) &= (A - \lambda I)^T P + P(A - \lambda I), \\ F_2(P, K) &= (4.7) - F_1(P) = PBK + K^T B^T P + 2\lambda P, \\ \lambda &> \max\{\operatorname{Re}\lambda(A)\}, \\ \mu &\in [0, 1]. \end{aligned}$$

At the first step (4.8) is solved with $\mu = 0$, which is very easy when using LMI software; in fact, although A is not stable, it's always possible to find a positive scalar λ such that $A - \lambda I$ is stable, and a way is by choosing $\lambda > \max\{\operatorname{Re}\lambda(A)\}$ as done above.

Then, with the obtained P , it's possible to set $\mu = 1$ and solve for K : at this point, (4.8) corresponds to the continuous time Lyapunov condition (4.7) for which the solution is sought.

If no solution is found, μ is increased progressively instead (for example, let $\mu = k/M$ ($k = 1, 2, \dots, M$) with a large M) and 4.8 is gradually solved with P and K being fixed alternately, until μ reaches 1.

4.1.3 The proposed method for the discrete time case

The discrete time Lyapunov condition (4.6)

$$(A + BK)P(A + BK)^T - P < 0$$

is also nonlinear in K and P . However, as shown in [21], with the change of variable $Y = KP$, the obtained equivalent condition

$$(AP + BY)P^{-1}(AP + BY)^T - P < 0 , \quad (4.9)$$

can be easily written as an LMI in P and Y .

In fact, according to the Schur Complement condition, (4.9) can be expressed as

$$\begin{bmatrix} P & (AP + BY)^T \\ (AP + BY) & P \end{bmatrix} > 0 . \quad (4.10)$$

With the change of variable, the structure imposed by the network on K (see (4.4)) becomes a constraint on YP^{-1} .

Similarly to the homotopy based method introduced for the continuous time case by Zhai *et al.*, a method consisting in solving iteratively an inequality for a properly designed matrix function F with the matrix variables being fixed alternatively (in this case Y and P) is proposed to solve (4.10) with the constraint on $K = YP^{-1}$:

$$F(P, Y, \mu) = \begin{bmatrix} P & (F_1P + \mu F_2)^T \\ (F_1P + \mu F_2) & P \end{bmatrix} > 0 , \quad (4.11)$$

where μ is again the increasing parameter over the iterations from 0 to 1, F_1 ensures that at the first iteration ($\mu = 0$) the inequality is feasible and F_2 that at the last iteration ($\mu = 1$) (4.11) corresponds to the inequality for which a solution is sought, that is (4.10) and so that $F_1P + F_2 = AP + BY$.

The inequality (4.11) at the first iteration

$$F(P, Y, \mu) = \begin{bmatrix} P & (F_1P)^T \\ F_1P & P \end{bmatrix} > 0 , \quad (4.12)$$

corresponds to the following inequality, which is indeed a discrete time Lyapunov condition:

$$F_1PF_1^T - P < 0 . \quad (4.13)$$

Even if A might be not stable, it's always possible to find a scalar α such that αA is stable (in the complex plane, eigenvalues must be in the unit circle); hence, with

$$F_1 = \alpha A , \quad \alpha \in [-1, 1] \quad (4.14)$$

the problem at the first iteration (4.12, 4.13) is feasible.

As mentioned above, $F_1P + F_2 = AP + BY$, thus

$$\alpha AP + F_2 = AP + BY \implies F_2 = (1 - \alpha)AP + BY . \quad (4.15)$$

To sum up:

$$F(P, Y, \mu) = \begin{bmatrix} P & (F_1 P + \mu F_2)^T \\ (F_1 P + \mu F_2) & P \end{bmatrix} > 0, \quad (4.11)$$

$$F_1 = \alpha A \quad (F_1 \text{ stable}), \quad (4.14)$$

$$F_2 = (1 - \alpha)AP + BY, \quad (4.15)$$

$$\mu \in [0, 1].$$

As for the continuous time case, it's possible to compute first P with $\mu = 0$, and then, since with P and its inverse P^{-1} fixed the constraint on $K = YP^{-1}$ is linear with respect on Y , to solve the inequality for Y with $\mu = 1$ and P fixed; if a solution can't be obtained in this manner, (4.11) is solved alternatively for P and for Y with μ increased gradually instead and in a way that feasibility is ensured at each iteration (e.g. $\mu = k/M$ ($k = 0, 1, \dots, M$) with M large enough).

It might be worth noting that if P is diagonal, Y has the same structure of K ; as shown afterwards, it also simplifies the computation of P^{-1} .

4.2 LMI parallel solver

In this section a parallel solver applied to the method proposed above, and in particular to each matrix variable (P , P^{-1} or Y , as in Section 4.1.3), is introduced.

Different parts of matrix variables are computed separately and in parallel, so that in a MAS the computation can be distributed among the agents.

As seen so far, homotopy based methods, starting from a modified problem that would otherwise be infeasible for the deployed software, allow to reach a solution with consecutive interpolations restoring step by step the original problem.

A similar scheme when a problem is not feasible is applied to the parallel solvers proposed in the following sections, where each computing agent can modify only an assigned part of the matrix variable in order to satisfy the inequality.

If a solution is not provided, a matrix, for example Z , can be added in the inequality to make the problem feasible; then the inequality is iteratively solved (and the matrix variable collectively updated) with Z being gradually decreased adequately until it represents a null contribute, so that the original problem is restored.

Related applications of the proposed solvers are described in the following chapter.

4.2.1 Parallel computation of P

In this case, the matrix function F is a function of P , with Y and μ being fixed:

$$F = F(P) = \begin{bmatrix} P & (F_1P + \mu F_2)^T \\ (F_1P + \mu F_2) & P \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} P & (\alpha AP + \mu((1-\alpha)AP + BY))^T \\ (\alpha AP + \mu((1-\alpha)AP + BY)) & P \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4.16)$$

with $F > 0$ to be satisfied as in Section 4.1.3 .

At the very first iteration (P computed for the first time), as mentioned in Section 4.1.3, $F > 0$ corresponds to

$$F_1PF_1^T - P < 0, \quad (4.17)$$

hence, since F_1 is stable by construction, there exists a symmetric $P > 0$ satisfying (4.17); for example, P can be initialized with a diagonal matrix with positive elements.

In the proposed parallel solver, each computing agent i solves the inequality by considering only the part of P assigned to it as a variable; the inequality for agent i , if solved for a variation of P (an initial P is available), becomes:

$$F(P + \Delta P^{(i)}) = F(P) + \Delta F^{(i)}(\Delta P^{(i)}) > 0, \quad (4.18)$$

where $\Delta F^{(i)}$ is related to the variation $\Delta P^{(i)}$ made by agent i on the entries of P assigned to it. Naturally, any constraint on P is considered by the agent that computes the affected entries.

Also, $\Delta F^{(i)} \geq 0$ since it's computed to solve the inequality, otherwise no variation is made by agent i on P ($\Delta P^{(i)} = 0$).

As shown above, F depends linearly on P , so variations of F depending on modifications of different entries of P can be summed to obtain the total variation ΔF ; since agents have no modifiable P elements in common with each other, by concurrently applying the variations on P from all the agents the resulting variation ΔF is the sum of the variations on F obtained by each agent, i.e.

$$\Delta F(\dots, \Delta P_j, \Delta P_{j+1}, \dots) = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} \Delta F^{(j)}(\Delta P_j), \quad (4.19)$$

where \mathcal{N} is the set of all the agents, and ΔP_j is the variation on P made by agent j :

$$\begin{bmatrix} \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \cdots & P_j & P_k & \cdots \\ \cdots & \cdots & P_i & \cdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \end{bmatrix} \longrightarrow \Delta P = \begin{bmatrix} \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \cdots & \Delta P_j & \Delta P_k & \cdots \\ \cdots & \cdots & \Delta P_i & \cdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4.20)$$

with P_j, P_i, P_k indicating here entries or blocks of P entries assigned respectively to agents j, i, k ; the variation on P individually made by agent j to obtain $\Delta F^{(j)}$ is therefore

$$\Delta P^{(j)} = \begin{bmatrix} \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \cdots & \Delta P_j & 0 & \cdots \\ \cdots & 0 & 0 & \cdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4.21)$$

namely elements can be non zero only in the entries assigned to j .

Since P must be symmetric, each agent should be assigned symmetrical entries of P . Furthermore, $\Delta F^{(i)} \geq 0$ for every agent i , so

$$F + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} \Delta F^{(j)} \geq F + \Delta F^{(i)} > 0, \quad (4.22)$$

that is: the maximum variation on F is obtained by applying the P variations from all the agents that solved their inequality $F + \Delta F^{(i)} > 0$, i.e. if more agents find a solution, considering their variations on P at the same time will still yield a solution to the global inequality $F + \Delta F > 0$; when all P variations are applied, in order for the new P to represent a solution it's sufficient that just one agent solved the inequality (in its entries).

Again, each agent can modify only the assigned entries while the others are fixed, and in order to find a solution this could be not enough.

Therefore, in case the problem can't be solved by any of the agents, a scheme allowing to gradually approach a solution in a parallel manner is proposed.

As previously mentioned, the inequality $F > 0$ can be made feasible by adding a positive definite matrix to F :

$$F(P) + Z > 0, \quad (4.23)$$

or, if F is computed with the available P and the inequality solved for ΔP instead of P ,

$$F(P + \Delta P) + Z = F + \Delta F(\Delta P) + Z > 0, \quad (4.24)$$

with $Z > 0$, that could be for example $Z = \gamma I$, where γ is a positive scalar and I the identity matrix. In this case (4.24) becomes:

$$F + \Delta F + \gamma I > 0, \quad (4.25)$$

which, using the notation above, from the point of view of an agent i can be expressed as

$$F(P + \Delta P^{(i)}) + \gamma I = F + \Delta F^{(i)} + \gamma I > 0. \quad (4.26)$$

Each agent $i \in \mathcal{N}$ computes in parallel with the others its solution to (4.25) via (4.26), and then updates all the other parts of P , meanwhile computed by the other agents; for each agent, F is therefore updated with $F + \Delta F$ (resulting from the variations on P , see (4.19)), where $F + \Delta F \geq F$ since, as previously said, when agent i can't find a solution it doesn't apply any variation on P ($\Delta P^{(i)} = 0$).

At this point, if (4.25) is not solved, γ is increased, otherwise it's possible to try to solve (4.25, 4.26) with a reduced γ : an iterative scheme can be set with γ progressively decreased with the aim to obtain a solution at each iteration (e.g. $\gamma = c \frac{d}{D}$ ($d = D, \dots, 2, 1, 0$) with c a positive scalar and D large enough).

Clearly, the inequality to be solved at the last iteration is $F > 0$, or $F + \Delta F > 0$ if ΔP is considered as variable.

This proposed scheme can also be seen as solving with consecutive stricter relaxations. Besides, since each agent attempts to solve for variations on different entries of the matrix variable P , a sort of "orthogonality" on this parallel computation is present, where different agents solve for different entries of the matrix variable, thus in a certain sense with no "overlapping contributions".

4.2.2 Parallel computation of the inverse (of P)

As seen in Section 4.1.3, in order to solve the inequality for Y satisfying the constraint on K , the inverse of P is needed being $K = YP^{-1}$.

If the solution sought for P (available to every agent) is diagonal, then P^{-1} is a diagonal matrix whereby each element (i, i) is the reciprocal of the corresponding element of P , namely $P^{-1}(i, i) = 1/P(i, i)$.

Hereafter, a general method that can be used also when P is not diagonal is introduced.

According to the definition of inverse matrix,

$$PP^{-1} = I, \quad (4.27)$$

where I is a $n \times n$ identity matrix, being P a real matrix of the same size. Also, by noticing that

$$z^T PP^{-1} z = z^T I z \quad \forall z \in \mathbb{R}^n \implies \quad (4.28)$$

$$z^T (PP^{-1} - I) z = 0 \quad \forall z \in \mathbb{R}^n \iff PP^{-1} - I = 0 \text{ or } PP^{-1} = I, \quad (4.29)$$

and that P is given, LMI software can be employed to compute P^{-1} .

In fact,

$$\begin{aligned} z^T (PP^{-1} - I) z = 0 \quad \forall z \in \mathbb{R}^n &\iff \\ z^T (PP^{-1} - I) z \geq 0 \wedge z^T (PP^{-1} - I) z \leq 0 \quad \forall z \in \mathbb{R}^n, &\quad (4.30) \end{aligned}$$

thus the problem can be expressed as

$$I \geq PP^{-1} \geq I, \quad (4.31)$$

with P^{-1} as variable.

Similarly to the scheme proposed for the computation of P , each agent solves the inequalities for a different part of P^{-1} , so each agent can modify the assigned entries starting from an initial P^{-1} and only when obtains a solution.

The inequalities are initially made feasible (they could be infeasible starting from the initial P^{-1}), and they are gradually restored to the original condition, e.g.:

$$(1 + \gamma)I \geq PP^{-1} \geq (1 - \gamma)I, \text{ or equivalently} \quad (4.32)$$

$$F_I = PP^{-1} \geq (1 - \gamma)I, \text{ and} \quad (4.33)$$

$$F_I = PP^{-1} \leq (1 + \gamma)I, \quad (4.34)$$

with γ a positive scalar which is progressively decreased until zero, for example $\gamma = c \frac{d}{D}$ with $d = D, \dots, 2, 1, 0$ and c a positive real number.

As in Section 4.1.3, when F_I , depending linearly on P^{-1} , doesn't satisfy the related inequality, the solution obtained by an agent i modifies P^{-1} so that $F_I + \Delta F_I^{(i)}$ satisfies it. Each agent modifies a different part of P^{-1} , hence like in Section 4.1.3 for ΔF (4.19), by applying the modifications on P^{-1} from all the agents at the same time,

$$\Delta F_I(\dots, \Delta P_j^{-1}, \Delta P_{j+1}^{-1}, \dots) = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} \Delta F_I^{(j)}(\Delta P_j^{-1}). \quad (4.35)$$

When initially PP^{-1} doesn't satisfy one of the inequalities (at least one of the two is always satisfied), a solution found by agent i implies the individual variation $\Delta F_I^{(i)}$, and PP^{-1} satisfying the inequalities (4.32).

However, by applying all the P^{-1} variations at the same time could result in a ΔF_I which makes PP^{-1} not satisfying the other inequality, as shown below.

In order to avoid that the new F_I still satisfies the inequalities, because it depends linearly on P^{-1} , an average of the non null modifications on P^{-1} can be applied instead:

$$\Delta F_I \left(\frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_f} \Delta P_j^{-1} \right) = \frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_f} \Delta F_I^{(j)}(\Delta P_j^{-1}), \quad (4.36)$$

where \mathcal{N}_f indicates the set of agents which computed a solution and N_s its cardinality; this ensures that the updated F_I satisfies the inequalities (4.32) since, as shown in the Appendix,

$$\max_{i \in \mathcal{N}_f} \Delta F_I^{(i)} \geq \frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_f} \Delta F_I^{(j)} \geq \min_{i \in \mathcal{N}_f} \Delta F_I^{(i)} \quad (4.37)$$

$$\implies (1 + \gamma)I \geq F_I + \max_{i \in \mathcal{N}_f} \Delta F_I^{(i)} \geq F_I + \frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_f} \Delta F_I^{(j)} \geq F_I + \min_{i \in \mathcal{N}_f} \Delta F_I^{(i)} \geq (1 - \gamma)I, \quad (4.38)$$

with $\Delta F_I^{(y)} = \max_{i \in \mathcal{N}_f} \Delta F_I^{(i)}$ indicating that $\Delta F_I^{(y)} - \Delta F_I^{(j)} \geq 0 \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_f$, while $\Delta F_I^{(y)} = \min_{i \in \mathcal{N}_f} \Delta F_I^{(i)}$ indicates that $\Delta F_I^{(y)} - \Delta F_I^{(j)} \leq 0 \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_f$.

Therefore, as done for the computation of P , with this collective update of F_I a new iteration with a reduced γ can take place when a solution is found, otherwise γ is increased, and an iterative scheme can be set.

Since P is symmetric and positive definite, P^{-1} also is, thus at the very first computation P^{-1} can be initialized with a symmetric and positive definite matrix, as any diagonal matrix with positive elements. It's reasonable to say that if P is initialized with the identity matrix, then also P^{-1} should be.

4.2.3 Parallel computation of Y

The procedure to compute Y is similar to the one proposed for P in Section 4.2.1.

In both cases $F > 0$ has to be solved, with F depending linearly on the matrix variable.

For each agent, the matrix variable is subject to linear constraints, which are related to the assignment of the entries and in this instance also to the structure of the gain $K = YP^{-1}$.

Additional constraints on Y are considered by the agent computing the involved entries.

The matrix function F , becomes a function of Y :

$$F = F(Y) = \begin{bmatrix} P & (F_1P + \mu F_2)^T \\ (F_1P + \mu F_2) & P \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} P & (\alpha AP + \mu((1-\alpha)AP + BY))^T \\ (\alpha AP + \mu((1-\alpha)AP + BY)) & P \end{bmatrix},$$

with P and μ being fixed.

With a similar notation used for the computation of P , each computing agent i solves in the assigned entries, i.e. for $\Delta Y^{(i)}$, the following inequality:

$$F + \Delta F^{(i)}(\Delta Y^{(i)}) > 0, \quad (4.39)$$

where $\Delta F^{(i)}(\Delta Y^{(i)}) \geq 0$ ($\Delta Y^{(i)} = 0$ if agent i doesn't find a solution); F is then updated with

$$F + \Delta F = F + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} \Delta F^{(j)} \geq F + \Delta F^{(i)} > 0. \quad (4.40)$$

At the beginning (no previous computation of Y), Y can be initialized with a random real matrix, or, since P could be diagonal, with a random real matrix having the same structure of K .

As in Section 4.2.1, when $F > 0$ can't be solved by any of the agents, an iterative scheme consisting in adding a term γI to F , where γ is a gradually decreased positive scalar, is followed.

Hence, each agent i solves the inequality

$$F(Y + \Delta Y^{(i)}) + \gamma I = F + \Delta F^{(i)} + \gamma I > 0. \quad (4.41)$$

Y is then collectively updated, γ reduced and the inequality solved again, until $\gamma = 0$.

The considerations made in Section 4.2.1, so for the parallel computation of P , apply also here. Moreover, it can also be noted that each row of K (global gain matrix) describes the gain or part of the gain of one agent, therefore rows of Y can be related to the same agent ($K = YP^{-1}$) and this can be considered for the assignment of the entries.

4.2.4 Comments

- The computations in the introduced distributed methods are made in parallel, however they could be performed also in series. In this case considerations made on collective variations are not needed, since parts of the matrix variable are not modified simultaneously but one after the other, where each part modification can still follow the described setting.
- With the sought gain structure, each agent can compute its stabilizing inputs independently from the others given the states and the inputs from which it depends.
- From the identification stage, to the gain computation and application, a method for completely distributed learning and control had been presented; moreover the controls, obtained in a distributed manner, derive from a globally stabilizing gain computed in a non-centralized manner.

Chapter 5

Implementation and experimental results

This chapter describes implementations of the introduced distributed methods and their applications to provided examples.

The results have been obtained in MATLAB[®], and the CVX package ([24], [25]) has been employed to solve the linear matrix inequalities.

5.1 Distributed Identification

In order to proceed with the identification of the global LTI system, properly collected data are needed; the first step is therefore to generate valid samples.

As said in Chapter 3,

$$X_{t,T} = [x_d(t) \quad x_d(t+1) \quad \dots \quad x_d(t+T-1)],$$

$$U_{t,T} = [u_d(t) \quad u_d(t+1) \quad \dots \quad u_d(t+T-1)],$$

$$T \geq (m+1)n + m,$$

where $x_d(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $u_d(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ are state samples and input samples at a time step t respectively. Starting from $t = 0$, the input is indicated with $U_{0,T}$ and it needs to be persistently exciting of order $n+1$.

If there aren't particular constraints on the input, $U_{0,T}$ ("U0T" in the code block below) can be any $m \times T$ matrix of random values, as done in [3] and [2].

```
% Generate input for the global system
```

```
U0T= rand(m,T); % m: #inputs of the global system
```

where `rand` returns uniformly distributed random numbers in the interval (0,1). The aim is to generate an input $U_{0,T}$ whose values are "diversified enough" to build an Hankel matrix that has the required rank, according to the order (Preliminaries, Chapter 2).

By definition, if the Hankel matrix satisfies the condition on the rank, the generated input is persistently exciting; the test is illustrated hereafter.

Other choices for the input could induce an higher degree of diversification of the orders of magnitude of the values:

```
UOT= (rand(m,T)) .* 10.^(-5+ 10*rand(m,T));
```

Considering that the input has to be persistently exciting of order $n + 1$, the Hankel matrix with $n + 1$ block rows (each of them with m rows) is built and it's checked that the rank is $m \cdot \text{order} = m(n + 1)$.

```
% Build Hankel

order= n+1; % n: #states of the global system

%Timestep indices
first_col_Hankel =1:1:order;
last_row_Hankel = order:1:T;
hankel_idx = hankel(first_col_Hankel,last_row_Hankel);

%Place input samples
%Fill row-wise
for i = 1:order
    HankelRow_idx = hankel_idx(i,:);
    HankelU((i-1)*m+1 : i*m, :) = UOT(:,HankelRow_idx);
end

%PE Test
if rank(HankelU)== m*(n+1)
    disp('Persistently exciting input')
else
    error('Input not P.E. ')
end
```

Obviously, the procedure can be repeated until a persistently exciting input is obtained.

Hereafter a test of the distributed identification method, given the discrete time model of the collective system $x(t + 1) = Ax(t) + Bu(t)$, is performed.

Thus, once a valid $U_{0,T}$ is generated, $X_{0,T}$ ($X0T$ in the code) and $X_{1,T}$ ($X1T$ in the code) can be computed.

```
%Computation of X0T and X1T
Xd(:,1) = x0;

for i = 1:T

    Xd(:,i+1) = A*Xd(:,i)+ B*UOT(:,i);

end

X0T = Xd(:,1:T);
X1T = Xd(:,2:T+1);
```

According to the proposed distributed identification in Chapter 3, each agent needs the collected data related to the states and inputs on which its dynamics depends.

In a scenario where each agent collects only data related to its own state and input, if an agent j depends on the state on input of another agent, then related data have to be communicated to j .

Following (3.17),

$$[B^{(j)} \ A^{(j)}] = \operatorname{argmin}_{[B^{(j)} \ A^{(j)}]} \left\| X_{1,T}^{(j)} - [B^{(j)} \ A^{(j)}] \begin{bmatrix} U_{0,T}^{(Dj)} \\ X_{0,T}^{(Dj)} \end{bmatrix} \right\|_{\mathbb{F}}, \quad (5.1)$$

with $[B^{(j)} \ A^{(j)}]$ being the input and state matrices of agent j , $X_{1,T}^{(j)}$ containing only j state data (rows), and $U_{0,T}^{(Dj)}, X_{0,T}^{(Dj)}$ data (rows) of input and states on which j depends, a loop can be implemented to identify each agent's dynamics separately, as done below with the use of YALMIP Toolbox [26] (for the minimization):

```
for j=1:N_agents % = number of agents

    %Data needed by agent j, where n_ag: #states of each agent
    agent_state_rows = (j-1)*n_ag+1 : 1 : j*n_ag;
    X1T_agent = X1T(agent_state_rows,:);

    dep_states_rows = find(states_dep(j,:));
    dep_input_rows = find(inputs_dep(j,:));

    XOT_Dagent = XOT(dep_states_rows,:);
    UOT_Dagent = UOT(dep_input_rows,:);

    %YALMIP toolbox settings and solve

    %Number of states and inputs on which agent j depends on
    N_dep = sum(states_dep(j,:))+sum(inputs_dep(j,:));
    %Variable declaration
    BAagent= sdpvar(n_ag, N_dep);

    %Frobenius norm to be minimized (5.1)
    cost = sum(sum((X1T_agent-BAagent*([UOT_Dagent;XOT_Dagent])).^2 ))

    %Solve
    sol(j,:)=optimize([],cost);

    %Save result
    BA.(["agent"+num2str(j)]) = value(BAagent);

end
```

where, referring to (5.1), $BAagent = [B^{(j)} \ A^{(j)}]$, $X1T_agent = X_{1,T}^{(j)}$, $XOT_Dagent = X_{0,T}^{(Dj)}$, and $UOT_Dagent = U_{0,T}^{(Dj)}$; $agent_state_rows$ contains the indices of the states of agent j in the collective state vector and $states_dep$ and $input_dep$ contain at row j the dependencies of state j on all states and inputs respectively.

In fact, $states_dep(j,k) = 1$ if the state of agent j (dynamics) depends on the state at k (entry) of the collective state vector (related collected data at k -th row of $X_{0,T}$ and of $X_{1,T}$), otherwise $states_dep(j,k) = 0$. Similarly, $inputs_dep(j,k) = 1$ if the state of agent j (dynamics) depends on the input at k (entry) of the collective input vector (related collected data at k -th row of $U_{0,T}$), otherwise $inputs_dep(j,k) = 0$; the function `find` returns the indices of nonzero elements, thus the needed dependencies. Furthermore, since the entries of these matrices are either 0 or 1, the sum of the elements of a j row yields the number of variables on which the state of agent j depends, i.e. the number of columns of $[B^{(j)} \ A^{(j)}]$ (see N_dep).

An application to a homogeneous 3-agent system is illustrated below.

In this example each agent depends only on its own input, on its state and on the state of another agents, as shown in Figure 5.1, where an arrow from agent i to agent j indicates that the state of agent i affects agent j dynamics. Thus the global system has form

$$\begin{bmatrix} x^{(1)} \\ x^{(2)} \\ x^{(3)} \end{bmatrix}_{t+1} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & 0 \\ 0 & A_{22} & A_{23} \\ A_{31} & 0 & A_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x^{(1)} \\ x^{(2)} \\ x^{(3)} \end{bmatrix}_t + \begin{bmatrix} B_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & B_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & B_3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u^{(1)} \\ u^{(2)} \\ u^{(3)} \end{bmatrix}_t, \quad (5.2)$$

with $x^{(i)}, u^{(i)} \in \mathbb{R}^2 \forall i \in \mathcal{N}$ (set of all the agents).

In this case, given the structure (adjacency matrices) and referring to the code,

$$\text{states_dep} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\text{inputs_dep} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix},$$

Figure 5.1:
State interdependencies
of the 3-agent system

and the 3 identifications are designed to result in:

$$[B^{(1)} \ A^{(1)}] = [B_1 \ A_{11} \ A_{12}],$$

$$[B^{(2)} \ A^{(2)}] = [B_2 \ A_{22} \ A_{23}],$$

$$[B^{(3)} \ A^{(3)}] = [B_3 \ A_{31} \ A_{33}].$$

Clearly, in this case `states_dep` and `inputs_dep` can also be inferred from the state and input matrices of the global system, here known a priori since this is a test of the distributed identification method.

For each agent, $n = m = 2$, thus referring to the global 3 agent system $n = m = 6$.

The computations have been made with $T = 50$, satisfying the requirement on T , which depends on the global system state and input dimensions :

$$T \geq (m + 1)n + m = (6 + 1)6 + 6 = 48.$$

5.1.1 Results

Hereafter, a comparison between the actual state and input matrices of the global system and the results of the identification ("A_ID", "B_ID") is made.

A =

1.0008e+00	1.0000e-03	1.0000e-04	1.5000e-04	0	0
3.0000e-04	1.0001e+00	2.0000e-05	1.0000e-04	0	0
0	0	1.0008e+00	1.0000e-03	1.0000e-04	1.5000e-04
0	0	3.0000e-04	1.0001e+00	2.0000e-05	1.0000e-04
1.0000e-04	1.5000e-04	0	0	1.0008e+00	1.0000e-03
2.0000e-05	1.0000e-04	0	0	3.0000e-04	1.0001e+00

A_ID =

1.0008e+00	1.0000e-03	9.9999e-05	1.5000e-04	0	0
2.9998e-04	1.0001e+00	2.0018e-05	9.9973e-05	0	0
0	0	1.0008e+00	1.0000e-03	9.9998e-05	1.5000e-04
0	0	3.0000e-04	1.0001e+00	2.0020e-05	9.9974e-05
9.9993e-05	1.5002e-04	0	0	1.0008e+00	9.9999e-04
1.9999e-05	1.0000e-04	0	0	3.0000e-04	1.0001e+00

B =

5.0000e-04	1.0000e-03	0	0	0	0
8.0000e-04	1.1000e-03	0	0	0	0
0	0	5.0000e-04	1.0000e-03	0	0
0	0	8.0000e-04	1.1000e-03	0	0
0	0	0	0	5.0000e-04	1.0000e-03
0	0	0	0	8.0000e-04	1.1000e-03

B_ID =

5.0000e-04	1.0000e-03	0	0	0	0
8.0000e-04	1.1000e-03	0	0	0	0
0	0	5.0000e-04	1.0000e-03	0	0
0	0	8.0000e-04	1.1000e-03	0	0
0	0	0	0	5.0000e-04	1.0000e-03
0	0	0	0	8.0000e-04	1.1000e-03

On the other hand, the centralized and so non-distributed identification based on (3.5) yields the following state and input matrices ("A_ND", "B_ND") :

A_ND =

1.0008e+00	9.9996e-04	1.0007e-04	1.4993e-04	5.0180e-08	-6.2623e-08
2.9976e-04	1.0001e+00	1.9634e-05	1.0047e-04	-2.9020e-07	3.7185e-07
-6.5121e-08	3.7065e-08	1.0008e+00	1.0002e-03	9.9908e-05	1.5012e-04
-7.9429e-08	4.1751e-08	2.9988e-04	1.0001e+00	1.9898e-05	1.0012e-04
9.9666e-05	1.5016e-04	-4.8624e-07	6.2501e-07	1.0008e+00	1.0005e-03
2.0071e-05	1.0000e-04	9.6114e-08	-1.4109e-07	3.0013e-04	1.0001e+00

B_ND =

5.0000e-04	1.0000e-03	-2.2310e-11	2.5169e-12	-1.8008e-11	-1.2188e-12
8.0000e-04	1.1000e-03	1.4168e-10	9.6338e-11	4.1363e-11	4.4464e-11
-1.1309e-11	5.4735e-12	5.0000e-04	1.0000e-03	8.6642e-12	8.363e-11
-1.6825e-11	1.2444e-11	8.0000e-04	1.1000e-03	1.1717e-11	4.8499e-12
-8.2452e-11	4.5620e-11	1.8880e-10	1.1733e-10	5.0000e-04	1.0000e-03
4.0394e-11	1.0287e-12	-3.9003e-11	-1.8024e-11	8.0000e-04	1.1000e-03

obtained with

```
BA = sdpvar(n,n+m);
cost = sum(sum( (X1T-BA*([U0T;X0T])).^2 ));
Constraints = []; % [-selection <= BA <= selection];
sol = optimize(Constraints, cost);
result = value(BA);
```

by activating the commented "Constraints", which take into account the structure of the solution (so the null submatrices in (5.2)), the results are identical to the ones from the distributed identification.

The table below displays the maximum relative relative errors recorded at different runs (different U0T and x0) on the non zero elements, in both the distributed ("maxErrD") and non-distributed ("maxErrND") identification cases (the latter without "Constraints", otherwise as said results are the same as the ones from the distributed identification case).

The maximum relative error is obtained as follows:

$$\max_{Entry} \left| \frac{IdentifiedEntry - Entry}{Entry} \right|,$$

where, as said, $Entry \neq 0$.

In the table, it can be observed that the ratio maxErrND/maxErrD is greater than 1 at each run. According to what said above, it means that the results of the distributed identification are more or equally accurate than the results of the non-distributed identification.

maxErrD	maxErrND	maxErrND/maxErrD
6.0079e-04	1.6011e-03	2.6650e+00
4.8568e-04	1.2898e-02	1.2107e+01
1.7577e-03	6.5476e-03	5.0821e+00
3.0686e-04	4.2434e-03	5.2999e+00
8.0954e-04	5.1905e-03	5.4642e+00
4.2313e-04	9.5461e-03	6.1274e+00
8.2140e-04	2.1632e-03	5.6818e+00
5.0579e-04	2.9229e-02	8.0856e+00
7.4337e-03	1.3436e-01	1.7163e+01
5.8790e-04	3.9411e-03	1.7104e+01

Table 5.1: Each row corresponds to a run and contains the maximum relative error among all the nonzero entries.

Furthermore, Figure 5.2 (hereunder) shows how a more diversified input produces better results.

Figure 5.2: maxErrD at runs with different U0T and T=50. To the left, the results are obtained with $U0T = \text{rand}(m, T)$, while to the right with $U0T = (-0.5+\text{rand}(m, T)).*10.^(-5+ 10*\text{rand}(m, T))$.

In order to observe the effect of the length T of the input UOT on the maximum relative error, distributed identifications (different UOT and x_0) have been performed increasing T (longer input), always ensuring that the input was persistently exciting.

The procedure have been repeated 4 times, then the obtained values have been averaged. The results are plotted below in Figure 5.3.

Figure 5.3: maxErrD (average over 4 experiments) at various T . Input generated with $UOT = \text{rand}(m, T)$ and $UOT = (-0.5 + \text{rand}(m, T)) \cdot 10.^{-5 + 10 \cdot \text{rand}(m, T)}$ to the left and to the right respectively.

Once again, from Figure 5.3 it can be noted that the more diversified input produced by $UOT = (-0.5 + \text{rand}(m, T)) \cdot 10.^{-5 + 10 \cdot \text{rand}(m, T)}$ is more effective.

In the experimented range, the results improve employing a larger T but only up to a certain threshold, in Figure 5.3 around 330.

5.1.2 From Local to Global System Identification

In the homogeneous 3-agent system, considered also in this section, the dynamics of each agent is a complete dynamics with respect to the global system.

As a matter of fact, since the system is homogeneous (state, input and coupling state matrices can't be different), (5.2) can be rewritten as

$$\begin{bmatrix} x^{(1)} \\ x^{(2)} \\ x^{(3)} \end{bmatrix}_{t+1} = \begin{bmatrix} A_o & A_c & 0 \\ 0 & A_o & A_c \\ A_c & 0 & A_o \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x^{(1)} \\ x^{(2)} \\ x^{(3)} \end{bmatrix}_t + \begin{bmatrix} B_o & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & B_o & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & B_o \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u^{(1)} \\ u^{(2)} \\ u^{(3)} \end{bmatrix}_t, \quad (5.3)$$

and it can be seen that each agent dynamics equation contains all the submatrices needed to "build" the global system equation: in fact the system is described by (3.18) and according to Corollary 2.3 every agent can derive the global equation from the local one, given the adjacency matrix for state interdependencies.

Once each agent identifies its local system, A_o , A_c and B_o are obtained; given the adjacency matrices for state and input coupling

$$\mathcal{A}_A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5.4)$$

$$\mathcal{A}_B = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5.5)$$

each agent can identify the global system by performing the following operations (Corollary 2.2):

$$A = I_3 \otimes A_o + \mathcal{A}_A \otimes A_o, \quad (5.6)$$

$$B = I_3 \otimes B_o. \quad (5.7)$$

5.2 Distributed Stabilization: gain computation

In Chapter 4 a method to compute a stabilizing gain with a structure set as distributed, implying that the input of an agent depends only on the states of agents affecting its dynamics, and in a parallel manner, has been introduced for the discrete time case.

As specified in Section 4.1.3, the gain K is computed by solving the following matrix inequality involving the matrix function F :

$$F = F(\mu, P, Y) = \begin{bmatrix} P & (\alpha AP + \mu((1 - \alpha)AP + BY))^T \\ (\alpha AP + \mu((1 - \alpha)AP + BY)) & P \end{bmatrix} > 0, \quad (5.8)$$

with $K = YP^{-1}$, $P > 0$ and symmetric.

The general scheme of the method, based on homotopy, is illustrated below in Algorithm 1; it is followed by all the agents, which compute P , P^{-1} and Y in a parallel manner via Algorithm 2, 3 and 4, described in the next sections.

Algorithm 1: Gain computation scheme

Result: Stabilizing gain K for the discrete time system

initialize M , $i = 1$;

while $i \leq M$ **do**

$\mu = (i - 1)/M$;

Solve $F > 0$ for P via Algorithm 2;

Compute P^{-1} via Algorithm 3;

$i = i + 1$;

$\mu = (i - 1)/M$; (at the last iteration here $\mu = 1 \implies (\text{loop increment}) \cdot (\# \text{loops} - 1) + 1 = M$)*

Solve $F > 0$ for Y via Algorithm 4 with constraint on $K = YP^{-1}$;

$i = i + 1$; (each loop increment is 2)

end

$K = YP^{-1}$;

*another loop won't be initiated since $i = M + 2$, that is $> M$

The value of M , a positive odd integer (see above), determines the steps that the algorithm needs to reach and solve the "original" discrete time problem, where $\mu = 1$.

With an higher M , μ is increased more gradually and it's easier for the algorithm to find a solution ([23]); however in this way more iterations are performed.

As said in Section 4.1.3, α ensures that the very initial problem, i.e. $F(P) > 0$ (for $P > 0$ and symmetric) with $\mu = 0$, is feasible and so that αA is stable; therefore, seen that

$$\alpha \geq 0 \implies \max |eig(\alpha A)| = \alpha \max |eig(A)|, \quad (5.9)$$

it's possible to set a proper value for the LHS $\max |eig(\alpha A)|$ (such that αA is stable) in the interval $[0,1)$ and obtain α ; for example:

```
desired_LHS = 0.5; % Value for the LHS of (5.9)
alpha = desired_LHS/max(abs(eig(A))) ;
```

Setting $M = 1$ means trying the quickest way to compute the desired gain, where first a P is computed with $\mu = 0$ (feasible because of α) and next, since μ directly becomes 1, the original problem is solved for Y with P fixed, allowing then to obtain K . However, as already explained, it's not said that a solution will be provided and a bigger M might be required.

In the following, the implementation of the parallel solvers (Algorithm 2, 3 and 4) are described, with application to the 3-agent system considered previously.

5.2.1 Parallel computation of P

In order to solve the inequality $F(P) > 0$, for a symmetric and positive definite P , each agent has to solve an inequality of the form proposed in (4.26), i.e.

$$F(P + \Delta P^{(i)}) + \gamma I = F + \Delta F^{(i)}(\Delta P^{(i)}) + \gamma I > 0, \quad (5.10)$$

where $\Delta P^{(i)}$ is the matrix variable of the inequality, that is the variation on P that an agent i can make only in the assigned entries ($\Delta P^{(i)}$ is zero in non assigned entries); $\Delta F^{(i)}$ the resulting variation of F ; γ is a nonnegative scalar, positive and decreased over iterations when these are needed (e.g. $\gamma = c \frac{d}{D}$ ($d = D, \dots, 2, 1, 0$) with c a positive scalar).

Algorithm 2: Distributed solver for $F(P) > 0$

Result: P

assign P entries to the agents ;

initialize D , c , and a symmetric $P > 0$ if no previously computed P is available ($\mu = 0$) ;

$\forall i$ in parallel:

for ($d = D$; $d \geq 0$; $d = d - 1$) {

$\gamma = c \frac{d}{D}$;

Solve (5.10) for $\Delta P^{(i)}$ (assigned entries);

if *No solution is found* **then**

$\Delta P^{(i)} = 0$

end

Update P with the other agents: $P + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} \Delta P^{(i)}$;

}

The pseudocode above summarises the proposed mechanism for the parallel computation of P .

Naturally each assigned part of P should contain the symmetric entries, in order to allow modifications of P on all the elements; this is illustrated in the application described hereafter, which refers to the 3-agent homogeneous system introduced in Section 5.1 .

In the considered system P can be partitioned in 9 blocks, and the proposed symmetric and equal (in number of entries) assignments for the agents, referred to as "1,2,3", are shown below :

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 2 \\ 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 2 & 3 & 3 \end{bmatrix} . \quad (5.11)$$

The following code indicates how the parallel solver can be reproduced.

At the very first computation of P , it is initialized with the identity matrix.

```

c = 1.2e-8;
%To simplify matrix function F
A1 = alpha*A; % alpha in (5.9)
A2 = (1-alpha)*A;

%P size = n x n (n:global system's states)
dimP = n_ag*N_agents ; %n_ag: each agent states, N_agents: number of agents

%CVX can't solve strict inequalities
tol = 1e-8;
I_LMI_F = eye(2*dimP); % >= tol*I_LMI_F instead of > 0
I_LMI_P = eye(dimP);

%Parallel solver
for d=0:D
    g = c*(1 - d/D); %gamma (5.10)
    DP=zeros(dimP); %initialize computed global variation
    PFIX=P; %P from the previous iteration

    % AGENT 1 P computation %
    cvx_begin sdp
        variable P(dimP,dimP) symmetric
        [
            P ( A1*P + u*(A2*P + B*Y) )';...
            (A1*P + u*(A2*P + B*Y)) P ] >= -g*I_LMI_F + tol*I_LMI_F

        P >= tol*I_LMI_P
        %Assignment : fix other agents entries
        P(3:6,3:6) == PFIX(3:6,3:6)
        P(1:2,5:6) == PFIX(1:2,5:6)
        P(5:6,1:2) == PFIX(5:6,1:2)
    cvx_end
    %Agent 1 contribute to global P variation DP
    if sum(sum(isnan(P)))>0 %Not valid solution
        DP = DP+0;
    else
        DP= DP+P-PFIX;
    end
    % AGENT 2 P computation %
    ...
    % AGENT 3 P computation %
    ...
    %Agent 3 contribute to global P variation DP
    if sum(sum(isnan(P)))>0
        DP = DP+0;
    else
        DP= DP+P-PFIX;
    end
    %Clearly, the computations made in parallel by the agents can also be reproduced
    %with a loop and using a matrix containing assignments %

    P = PFIX + DP; %New P
end

```

In the loop, agent 2 and 3 computation have a similar scheme, with only the entries' assignment section being different; u indicates μ .

5.2.2 Parallel computation of P^{-1}

The inverse matrix P^{-1} is the matrix variable for which the inequalities (4.33), (4.34) are solved:

$$PP^{-1} \geq (1 - \gamma)I, \quad (5.12)$$

$$PP^{-1} \leq (1 + \gamma)I. \quad (5.13)$$

Following the results obtained in Section 4.2.2, the scheme for computing the inverse matrix in a parallel manner is shown below.

Algorithm 3: Distributed computation of the inverse

Result: P^{-1}

assign P^{-1} entries to the agents ;

initialize D , c , and P^{-1} if a previously computed one is not available ;

$\forall i$ in parallel:

for ($d = D$; $d \geq 0$; $d = d - 1$) {

$\gamma = c \frac{d}{D}$;

 Solve (5.12) and (5.13) for ΔP_i^{-1} (for assigned entries of P^{-1}):

$P \cdot (P^{-1} + \Delta P_i^{-1}) \geq, \leq (1-, +\gamma) \cdot I$;

 Made_Variation(i) = 1 ;

if *No solution is found* **then**

$\Delta P_i^{-1} = 0$;

 Made_Variation(i) = 0 ;

end

 Update Tot_Variation and then P^{-1} with the other agents:

 Tot_Variations = $\sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} \text{Made_Variation}(i)$;

if *Tot_Variation* $\neq 0$ **then**

$P^{-1} = P^{-1} + \frac{1}{\text{Tot_Variation}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} \Delta P_i^{-1}$ (4.34);

end

}

An implementation for the 3-agent system considered in the previous sections, where each agent is assigned an equal number of columns of the matrix variable, can be:

```

I_P = eye(dimP); %For the inequalities, dimP = length of P
DPinv_each= []; %Variable collecting every agent variation
c = 0.8;

for d=0:D
    if No_Previous_Pinv ==1 % No previously computed inverse available
        Pinv = I_P;
        No_Previous_Pinv = 0;
    end

    gamma=c*(1-d/D) ;
    PinvFIX=Pinv;

    made_variations=0; %Agents variations counter
    DPINV= zeros(dimP); %Will contain the total variation at the end of the iteration

    %AGENT 1
    cvx_begin sdp
        variable DPinv(dimP,dimP)

```

```

P*(DPinv+PinvFIX) >= (1-gamma)*I_P
P*(DPinv+PinvFIX) <= (1+gamma)*I_P

DPinv(1:end,3:end) == 0 %Assignment, here column wise

cvx_end

if sum(sum(isnan(DPinv)))>0 %Not valid solution
    DPinv_each(:,:,1) = zeros(dimP);
else
    DPinv_each(:,:,1) = DPinv;
    made_variations = made_variations + 1;
end

% AGENT 2
...
%AGENT 3
...
    made_variations = made_variations + 1;
end

%Also here, the computations made in parallel by the agents can also be reproduced
%with a loop and using a matrix containing assignments %

%Total variation made by agents
for ag = 1 : N_agents
    DPINV = DPinv_each(:,:,ag) + DPINV;
end

%Average as in (4.36) , avoid 0/0 division
if made_variations ~= 0
    DPINV =DPINV/made_variations;
end

Pinv = PinvFIX + DPINV ;

end

```

Apart of the entries' assignments, agent 2 and 3 have the same implementation.

5.2.3 Parallel computation of Y

As already seen in Chapter 4, solving $F > 0$ for Y or for Y represent the same type of problem: F linearly depends on the matrix variable, which is subject to linear constraints. Hence, the parallel solver described in this section is similar to the one described for $F(P) > 0$ in Section 5.2.1.

According to (4.41), each agent has to solve the inequality

$$F(Y + \Delta Y^{(i)}) + \gamma I = F + \Delta F^{(i)}(\Delta Y^{(i)}) + \gamma I > 0, \quad (5.14)$$

where $\Delta Y^{(i)}$ is the matrix variable of the inequality, that is the variation on Y that an agent i can make only in the assigned entries ($\Delta Y^{(i)}$ is zero in non assigned entries); $\Delta F^{(i)}$ the resulting variation of F ; γ is a nonnegative scalar, positive and decreased over iterations when these are needed (e.g. $\gamma = c \frac{d}{D}$ ($d = D, \dots, 2, 1, 0$) with c a positive scalar).

As said before, each row of K (global gain matrix) describes the gain or part of the gain of one agent, therefore rows of Y can be related to the same agent ($K = YP^{-1}$).

Algorithm 4: Distributed solver for $F(Y) > 0$

Result: Y

assign Y rows to the related agents ($K = YP^{-1}$);

initialize D , c , and Y if not previously computed (random or with K structure);

$\forall i$ in parallel:

for ($d = D$; $d \geq 0$; $d = d - 1$) {

$\gamma = c \frac{d}{D}$;

Solve (5.14) for $\Delta Y^{(i)}$ in the assigned rows and satisfying related constraints (K);

if *No solution is found* **then**

| $\Delta Y^{(i)} = 0$

end

Update Y with the other agents: $Y + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} \Delta Y^{(i)}$;

}

By assigning to each agent computations related to its gain (rows) and so the related rows of Y , the constraints are also expressed for the different rows of Y , considering P^{-1} as a constant:

$$K(\text{row}, :) = Y(\text{row}, :)P^{-1}. \quad (5.15)$$

The scheme illustrated by Algorithm 4 is applied to the 3-agent system introduced in Section 5.1, from which the distributed structure to impose on K can be inferred and is described by the matrix below:

$$K_{struct} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5.16)$$

in which zeros indicate positions where K entries must be zero, and ones positions where K entries can be nonzero.

A proposed implementation for simulating the parallel computation of Y , with elements from the implementation for P , is:

```

%Y size = n x m (n,m are the global system's states and inputs)
rowY = m_ag*N_agents ; %m_ag: each agent inputs, N_agents: number of agents
colY = n_ag*N_agents ; %n_ag: each agent states

%Y initialization
Y = -0.5+rand(rowY,colY);

%Parallel solver
for d=0:D
    g = c*(1 - d/D);      %gamma, as in (5.14)
    DY=zeros(rowY,colY); %initialize computed collective variation of Y
    YFIX=Y;               %Y from the previous iteration

    % AGENT 1 Y computation %
    cvx_begin sdp
        variable Y(rowY,colY)
        [
            P
            (A1*P + u*(A2*P + B*Y))
            (A1*P + u*(A2*P + B*Y))
            P
        ] >= -g*I_LMI_F + tol*I_LMI_F

        %Assignment : fix other agents rows
        Y(3:end,1:end) == YFIX(3:end,1:end)

        %Constraint on agent 1 gain (same rows of Y)
        %K(1:2,5:end) == 0, agent 1 input doesn't depend on agent 3 states
        Y(1:2,:)*Pinv(:,5:end) == 0 %Pinv is the inverse of P

    cvx_end
    %Agent 1 contribute to the collective variation DY
    if sum(sum(isnan(Y)))>0 %Not valid solution
        DY = DY+0;
    else
        DY= DY+Y-YFIX;
    end
    % AGENT 2 Y computation %
    ...
    % AGENT 3 Y computation %
    ...
    %Agent 3 contribute to the collective variation DY
    if sum(sum(isnan(Y)))>0
        DY = DY+0;
    else
        DY= DY+Y-YFIX;
    end
    %Also here, the computations made in parallel by the agents can also be reproduced
    %with a loop and using a matrix containing assignments %

    Y = YFIX + DY; %New Y
end

```

In the loop, agent 2 and 3 computation have a similar scheme, with only the entries' assignment section and the related constraints being different.

5.2.4 Results

The state matrix A of the 3-agent system is unstable ($\max \|\lambda\| \approx 1.0013$). In order to make the problem initially feasible, `desired_LHS = 0.5` has been used (implying $\alpha \approx 0.4994$, see (5.9)).

Apart of M (Algorithm 1), the parameters employed for the implementation of the algorithms are contained in the table below.

Algorithm 2: $F(P) > 0$	$P(\mu = 0) = I$, $D = 2(3 \text{ iter.})$, $c = 1.2e - 8$, <code>tol= 1e - 8</code>
Algorithm 3: P^{-1}	$P^{-1}(\mu = 0) = I$, $D = 60(61 \text{ iter.})$, $c = 0.8$
Algorithm 4: $F(Y) > 0$	$Y(\mu = 0) = \text{random}^*$, $D = 2(3 \text{ iter.})$, $c = 1.2e - 8$, <code>tol= 1e - 8</code>

*Initialized as in the code (with `"-0.5+rand(rowY,colY)"`).

A stabilizing gain has been obtained even with $M = 1$, thus with only one "homotopy (Algorithm 1) iteration".

In this case, with the resulting gain $\max\{\|\lambda(A + BK)\|\} \approx 2.6284e - 6$, starting from $\max\{\|\lambda(A + BK)\|\} \approx 1.002$ (K obtained after the first P and P^{-1} computation, so with $\mu = 0$ and the initialized random Y) and $\max\{\|\lambda(A_1 + \mu(A_2 + BK))\|\} = \max\{\|\lambda(A_1)\|\} = 0.5$ (`=desired_LHS`).

Numerical experiments to obtain a solution more gradually have been performed, starting from the same initial Y , with $M = 3$ and $M = 13$. As μ varies, the resulting system dynamics, in terms of largest eigenvalue in magnitude of $A + BK$ and of $A_1 + \mu(A_2 + BK)$, is illustrated in Figure 5.4 and 5.5.

$A_1 + \mu(A_2 + BK)$ represents the system for which a solution is sought, with μ progressively increased and corresponding to $A + BK$ when μ finally reaches 1.

As a matter of fact, $F > 0$ corresponds to the condition (see Section 4.1.3)

$$(A_1 P + \mu(A_2 P + B Y)) P^{-1} (A_1 P + \mu(A_2 P + B Y))^T - P < 0 \implies$$

$$(A_1 + \mu(A_2 + B Y P^{-1})) P (A_1 + \mu(A_2 + B Y P^{-1}))^T - P < 0 \implies$$

$$(A_1 + \mu(A_2 + B K)) P (A_1 + \mu(A_2 + B K))^T - P < 0,$$

where $A_1 = \alpha A$ and $A_2 = (1 - \alpha)A$, as in Section 5.2.1 (code).

Figure 5.4: Largest eigenvalue ("λ") in magnitude of $A + BK$ and of $A_1 + \mu(A_2 + BK)$ as a function of μ , in both cases around $6.1398e - 06$ at $\mu = 1$. Run with $M = 3$.

Figure 5.5: Largest eigenvalue ("λ") in magnitude of $A+BK$ and of $A_1 + \mu(A_2+BK)$ as a function of μ , in both cases around $5.9775e-06$ at $\mu=1$. Run with $M=13$.

The proposed method to compute a stabilizing gain has been applied also to a similar multi-agent LTI homogenous system, described by the same block matrices A_o , A_c , B_o (global input matrix B is block diagonal), and consisting of 9 agents.

The interdependencies between the states of different agents derive from a Watts-Strogatz network [27] with 9 nodes, illustrated in Figure 5.6.

About the computations, the assignment of matrix variable entries have been made with the same approach used for the 3-agent system, and the same parameters have been employed.

Figure 5.6:
Each node represents an agent, and an edge represents mutual dependence of the connected agents' states

Also in this case, it has been possible to reach a solution with $M=1$.

With the obtained gain, $\max\{\|\lambda(A+BK)\|\} = 7.2428e-5$, while initially $\max\{\|\lambda(A+BK)\|\} = 1.0018$ and $\max\{\|\lambda(A1)\|\} = \text{desired_LHS} = 0.5$.

Similarly to the 3-agent system case, the variation with μ of the largest eigenvalue in magnitude, using $M=3$ and $M=13$, is plotted in Figure 5.8 and 5.9.

K =

4.4023e+03	-3.9960e+03	3.7273e-01	2.6919e-01	0	0
-3.2020e+03	1.9970e+03	-2.8990e-01	-2.8988e-01	0	0
0	0	4.4023e+03	-3.9960e+03	3.7275e-01	2.6918e-01
0	0	-3.2020e+03	1.9970e+03	-2.8991e-01	-2.8988e-01
3.7811e-01	2.7306e-01	0	0	4.4023e+03	-3.9960e+03
-2.9408e-01	-2.9405e-01	0	0	-3.2020e+03	1.9970e+03

Figure 5.7: Gain obtained with $M=3$, 3-agent system case.

Figure 5.8: Largest eigenvalue ("λ") in magnitude of $A+BK$ and of $A_1 + \mu(A_2+BK)$ as a function of μ , in both cases around $5.7701e - 04$ at $\mu = 1$. Run with $M = 3$.

Figure 5.9: Largest eigenvalue ("λ") in magnitude of $A+BK$ and of $A_1 + \mu(A_2+BK)$ as a function of μ , in both cases around $1.6037e - 04$ at $\mu = 1$. Run with $M = 13$.

In both cases, an oscillation of $\max\{\|\lambda(A_1 + \mu(A_2 + BK))\|\}$ can be observed, as $(A_1 + \mu(A_2 + BK))P(A_1 + \mu(A_2 + BK))^T - P < 0$ is solved alternatively for P and Y , with μ increased in between (see Algorithm 1). It can be seen also that the oscillations occur around a value that is approximately constant, and this can be related to the fact that the mentioned inequality is solved each time with the same value for τ_{ol} .

The same can't be said for $\max\{\|\lambda(A + BK)\|\}$, which, starting from an higher value, gradually approaches $\max\{\|\lambda(A_1 + \mu(A_2 + BK))\|\}$ with the increase of μ , seen that $A_1 + \mu(A_2 + BK)$ and $A + BK$ become closer as μ goes from 0 to 1.

The computation of the inverse required an higher amount of iterations ($D = 60$, Algorithm 3) than the ones needed to solve the inequalities for P and for Y ($D = 2$, Algorithm 2 and 4).

Chapter 6

Conclusions and future work

In this thesis, two major problems have been addressed: the Distributed System Identification and the Distributed Stabilization of Linear Time Invariant multi-agent systems.

In addition, a parallel solver for Linear Matrix Inequalities has been proposed, in order to have that also the computation of the stabilizing gain can be performed in a manner which is not centralized.

Conditions to enable the Distributed Identification from properly collected data and using a persistently exciting input have been derived; it has also been shown that in a homogeneous multi-agent system, an agent described by a so-called complete dynamics equation can identify the global dynamics equation from local identification, if the adjacency matrices describing state and input interdependencies are given.

In order to compute a gain enabling closed-loop distributed stabilization, a homotopy-based method has been introduced to solve the nonlinear multi-agent system discrete time Lyapunov condition, which has not been well studied, with LMI solvers.

A scheme to resolve Linear Matrix Inequalities in parallel has also been proposed.

It's based on consecutive relaxations when an inequality is initially not feasible for any of the different computing agents, which are assigned the computation of different parts of the matrix variable.

The obtained results have been successfully tested via numerical experiments performed with the described implementations.

6.1 Future work

There are several ways to extend the results of this work.

For instance, in order to proceed with the distributed identification a persistently exciting global input is needed, and ways to generate one in a non centralized and distributed manner have to be investigated.

Also, the computation of the stabilizing gain and the LMI parallel solver rely on parameters as μ and γ , which are increased or decreased over the iterations with constant variations. It might be more efficient to use variations which change over the iterations; finding adequate parameters D and c (parallel solvers) is another interesting point.

Naturally, the use of noisy data for the identification, and the extension of the proposed distributed identification and stabilization to noisy and nonlinear systems in general is still to be studied.

Last but not least, another interesting direction would be to look for modifications on the introduced parallel solver scheme which can make the solver distributed. For example, a distributed communication protocol for the local update (also asynchronous) of the whole matrix variable could be added, and the computing agents could be allowed to have different updates of the parameter γ .

Appendix A

Notation - Section 4.2.2

The notation in Section 4.2.2

$$\max_{i \in \mathcal{N}_f} \Delta F_I^{(i)}$$

in

$$\max_{i \in \mathcal{N}_f} \Delta F_I^{(i)} \geq \frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_f} \Delta F_I^{(j)} \geq \min_{i \in \mathcal{N}_f} \Delta F_I^{(i)}$$

indicates, with $\Delta F_I^{(y)} = \max_{i \in \mathcal{N}_f} \Delta F_I^{(i)}$, that

$$\Delta F_I^{(y)} - \Delta F_I^{(j)} \geq 0 \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_f .$$

By considering the sum of all the matrices $\Delta F_I^{(y)} - \Delta F_I^{(j)}$ ($\forall j \in \mathcal{N}_f$), it can be noted that

$$N_s \Delta F_I^{(y)} - \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_f} \Delta F_I^{(j)} \geq 0 \implies \Delta F_I^{(y)} - \frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_f} \Delta F_I^{(j)} \geq 0 \implies F_I + \Delta F_I^{(y)} \geq F_I + \frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_f} \Delta F_I^{(j)} .$$

Similarly, with $\Delta F_I^{(y)} = \min_{i \in \mathcal{N}_f} \Delta F_I^{(i)}$,

$$\Delta F_I^{(y)} - \Delta F_I^{(j)} \leq 0 \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_f ,$$

and

$$F_I + \frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_f} \Delta F_I^{(j)} \geq F_I + \Delta F_I^{(y)} .$$

Since the inequalities (4.33),(4.34) are solved with the variations $\Delta F_I^{(j)} \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_f$,

$$(1 + \gamma)I \geq F_I + \max_{i \in \mathcal{N}_f} \Delta F_I^{(i)} \geq F_I + \frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_f} \Delta F_I^{(j)} \geq F_I + \min_{i \in \mathcal{N}_f} \Delta F_I^{(i)} \geq (1 - \gamma)I .$$

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